

Full Length Article

Enhancing guard-ring protection structures for the next generation of radiation-hard thin silicon particle detectors

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ABSTRACT

Future hadron collider experiments (e.g. FCC-hh) will require highly efficient silicon particle detectors able to operate in extremely harsh radiation environments ($\sim 10^{17}$ $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$). The guard-ring (GR) protection structures are an essential part of the sensor. They have to sustain a large external bias with minimal leakage current injection into the core region, making their design and optimisation crucial, especially when using thin sensor substrates. In the framework of the “eXFlu-innova” research project (AIDAInnova), different GR optimisation studies for both p- and n-type thin substrates (ranging from 15 to 55 μm) have been conducted up to high fluences (above 10^{15} $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$). These studies have been made possible thanks to ad-hoc Technology CAD (TCAD) modelling of various GR design strategies, accounting for comprehensive bulk and surface radiation-induced damage effects. Moreover, an extensive test campaign on such GR structures has been performed, both before and after irradiation. Leveraging the recently obtained agreement between simulated and experimental data for p-type substrates, both before and after irradiation, the validated development framework was extended to simulate GR design options for n-type substrates as well. This contribution provides a summary of the GR optimisation studies for both p- and n-type substrates and their impact on performance.

1. Introduction

The next generation of high-energy physics (HEP) experiments at future hadron colliders (e.g. FCC-hh) will require the use of highly efficient silicon tracking detectors capable of operating in extremely harsh radiation environments ($\sim 10^{17}$ $1 \text{ MeV } n_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$) [1]. The design of particle detectors able to withstand extreme fluences would benefit from the use of thin substrates (20–40 μm), which are intrinsically more resistant to radiation, as its effects directly depend on the sensor volume [2]. The guard-ring (GR) protection structures are an essential part of the sensor, which must operate under a large external bias with minimal leakage current injection into the core region, making their design and optimisation crucial, especially when using thin bulk thicknesses.

In the framework of the “eXFlu-innova” research project (AIDAInnova), various GR optimisation studies for both p- and n-type thin substrates have been conducted. These studies have been enabled thanks to ad-hoc Technology CAD (TCAD) modelling and simulation of GR structures, accounting for different design strategies (e.g. zero-guard and multi-guard structures), extension of the periphery region, as well as the comprehensive bulk and surface radiation-induced damage effects [3]. Moreover, an extensive test campaign, including current-voltage (I-V) and “popcorn” noise measurements, has been performed on various GR structures, which were produced within the “EXFLU1” R&D batch by Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK) in Trento, using p-type substrates of different thicknesses (45, 30, 20, and 15 μm) [4].

Thanks to the good agreement between the simulated and measured I-V curves and breakdown voltages under different operating conditions

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Fig. 1. Shot of GR designs (S1–S16) from the “EXFLU1” R&D batch, with a schematic description of each feature (details are covered by a non-disclosure agreement with FBK).

Table 1

Name and description of the GR designs coming from the “EXFLU1” R&D batch produced at FBK in the framework of the “eXFlu” project.

GR design	Description
S2–S9	GR0: no floating GR, varying metal overhang, periphery and void region size
S10–S13	GR1: one floating GR, varying its position with respect to the BR
S14–S16	GR3: three floating GRs, using one of or both n-deep and p-stop implants
S1	GR4: four floating GRs. Standard design, used in previous batches [6]

(i.e. temperature, T , and fluence, Φ), the simulation framework has been validated [5]. This validation has enabled a new series of simulations recently conducted on different GR design strategies optimised for 55 μm -thick n-type substrates, providing inputs to guide the design of the ongoing sensor production at FBK, as will be presented here.

2. Devices under test, experimental setups, and methods

P-i-n sensors with high-resistivity p-type epitaxial bulk, coming from the first R&D batch of the “eXFlu” project produced at FBK and called “EXFLU1”, were first considered for this study [4]. These sensors feature an active area of $1.3 \times 1.3 \text{ mm}^2$, four different bulk thicknesses (45, 30, 20, and 15 μm), and sixteen GR design strategies (S1–S16) optimised to shape the electric field and reduce the noise impact during the sensor operation. In particular, these designs differ in the number of floating GRs, namely zero (GR0), one (GR1), three (GR3), and four (GR4), that use one of or both n-deep and p-stop implants, their position between the Bias Ring (BR) and the scribeline (SL), extension of the metal overhangs and of the overall periphery region (see Fig. 1, and Table 1). A total of 576 samples were irradiated at the TRIGA Mark II research nuclear reactor, operated by the Jozef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana (Slovenia). Specifically, three samples per bulk thickness and GR design were irradiated at different fluence levels, namely 0.8, 1.5 and $2.5 \times 10^{15} \text{ MeV n}_{\text{eq}}/\text{cm}^2$, to ensure robust statistics for the measurements. After irradiation, the samples were annealed for 80 min at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. The electrical characterisation of the different GR designs before and after irradiation was performed at the Physics Department of Torino University.

2.1. Current-voltage and breakdown measurements

A temperature-controlled probe station (MPI TS200-SE, $-60/300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) connected to a power device analyser (Keysight B1505) was used to extract the breakdown voltage, V_{BD} , and the leakage current, I_{leak} ,

Fig. 2. Breakdown voltage, V_{BD} , of all the GR designs as a function of the fluence, Φ , for two different sensor thicknesses (20 and 30 μm).

from the current–voltage (I–V) characteristics. The samples were fixed directly on a chuck using a vacuum system, which provided the high reverse bias (i.e. a negative voltage for the n-in-p sensors tested). During the electrical characterisation the pad was connected to the ground, and a high current-resolution Medium Power Source and Monitor Unit (MP-SMU) was connected to the GR under test. Further details about the I–V setup can be found in [6].

Fig. 2 shows the V_{BD} of all the GR designs as a function of the fluence, Φ , for two different sensor thicknesses (20 and 30 μm). The GR structures without any floating GR (S2–S9 GR0) have almost the same breakdown voltage of the ones characterised by one (S10–S13 GR1) and three (S14–S16 GR3) floating GRs, both before and after irradiation. In particular, an improvement of the breakdown voltage in the GR0 structures has been obtained due to the increase of the overhang size of the metal contact over the bias ring (S5 GR0). This proves that GR structures without any floating GR implants are a viable design option.

2.2. Popcorn noise measurements

Popcorn Noise (PN) is a type of noise in detectors characterised by random and sudden peaks in the output signal, which lead to spikes in amplitude in the absence of external stimuli. The presence of such current spikes can degrade the signal stability and the sensor timing resolution [7].

To investigate the occurrence of this type of noise depending on the GR design and the fluence, the measurements of the non-irradiated samples were performed within a dark box at room temperature, and the ones of the irradiated samples were performed inside a climate chamber at temperatures down to $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Each sample was directly bonded onto a “Mignone” passive readout board from INFN Torino and connected to an amplification stage (Cividec Broadband Amplifier, 40 dB gain and 2 GHz bandwidth). The sensor signals were acquired using a four-channels WaveRunner 640ZI Teledyne LeCroy digital oscilloscope, characterised by a 40 GSamples/s sampling rate and a 4 GHz bandwidth. High-Voltage (HV) and Low-Voltage (LV) power supplies were used to bias the samples and the amplifier, respectively. The popcorn noise voltage, V_{PN} , was measured by gradually increasing the HV while monitoring the oscilloscope for the appearance of amplitude spikes.

Fig. 3 shows that, for some of the 30 μm -thick samples, V_{PN} , when observed, exceeds the single-event burnout (SEB) limit, i.e. the maximum electric field that can operate in the bulk under exposure to particle beams, and increases with fluence [8]. Furthermore, in most cases, the noise appears close to V_{BD} , ensuring the absence of spurious signals during sensor operation. S1 GR4, which represents the standard design used in previous R&D batches [6], was found to be the least effective GR configuration in this context. Fig. 4 illustrates that, even in the 20 μm -thick pre-irradiated samples, V_{PN} exceeds the SEB limit and is expected to increase further with irradiation.

Fig. 3. Measurements of breakdown and popcorn noise voltage for some of the 30 μm -thick GR structures as a function of fluence. The red dashed line represents the SEB limit and its uncertainty (red shaded).

Fig. 4. Measurements of breakdown and popcorn noise voltage for all the 20 μm -thick GR structures before irradiation. The red dashed line represents the SEB limit and its uncertainty (red shaded).

Fig. 5. Layout of a 55 μm -thick GR1 protection structure implemented in the 2D domain of the Synopsys[®] Sentaurus TCAD.

Table 2

Name and description of the simulated GR designs for n-type bulk.

GR design	Description
S1, S3, S5	GR0: no floating GR, varying metal overhang
S6-S8	GR1: one floating GR, varying its position and metal overhang
S10	GR3: three floating GRs, using of single p-deep implant

Fig. 6. Simulated I-V curves of S1-S10 GR designs on 55 μm -thick n-type substrate before irradiation (298 K).

3. TCAD simulation results

The layouts of the different GR protection structures were implemented in a 2D domain by using state-of-the-art TCAD suite of tools. Details about the epitaxial thickness, doping concentration values, and the physical models used in the simulations — such as the “Perugia Modified Doping” TCAD radiation damage model [3], which accounts for combined bulk and surface radiation damage effects, and saturation of the acceptor-creation mechanism in the epitaxial — can be found in [5].

3.1. P-type substrates

A good agreement was observed for most GR design strategies regarding V_{BD} and the increase in I_{leak} with fluence [5]. In particular, it was confirmed that the GR0 structures exhibited a breakdown voltage comparable to the GR1 and GR3 designs both before and after irradiation. Furthermore, higher breakdown voltages can be achieved by increasing the overhang extension of the metal contact over the bias ring.

3.2. N-type substrates

Using the validated framework, a new series of simulations has been produced on different GR design strategies optimised for 55 μm -thick n-type substrates. Specifically, ten distinct designs (S1-S10) were developed, differing in the number of floating GRs (GR0, GR1, and GR3) that use a single p-deep implant, their position between the BR and the SL, and the extension of the metal overhangs. Fig. 5 shows an example of the layout of a GR1 protection structure implemented in 2D, while Table 2 provides the names and descriptions of the different simulated GR designs. To account for a p-in-n doping profile, the species were inverted with respect to the n-in-p counterpart, while maintaining the same relative concentration values.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the simulated I-V curves and the corresponding V_{BD} for all p-in-n GR designs before irradiation. The simulations were performed at 298 K using the Massey avalanche model, which was also employed for n-in-p GR structures. The curves clearly demonstrate that the S8 GR1 design achieves a higher V_{BD} compared to all other GR designs. This observation is corroborated by the electric field profiles shown in Fig. 8. The reduction in the distance between the floating GR and the BR minimises the electric field peak near the p-type implant of the BR, resulting in an increased breakdown voltage in the GR1 structures. In general, the V_{BD} values of S3 GR0, S7 GR1, and S10 GR3, as well as those of S1 GR0 and S6 GR1, are comparable. These GR

Fig. 7. Simulated breakdown voltage values of S1-S10 GR designs on 55 μm -thick n-type substrate before irradiation (298 K).

Fig. 8. Simulated electric field profiles at breakdown voltage, plotted as a function of the position along the surface region of the GR structure, 100 nm below the silicon-oxide interface, for GR1 design options S6, S7, and S8.

designs differ only in the number of floating GRs, while the extension of the metal overhangs remains unchanged. This confirms that GR0 structures are a viable design option for p-in-n structures. Lastly, the S5 GR0 structure exhibits the lowest V_{BD} due to a non-optimal extension of the overhang over the bias ring, which does not reduce the electric field peak near the p-type implant of the bias ring, as observed in the n-in-p structures. Further investigations are required in this regard.

4. Conclusions

The I-V characteristics and breakdown voltages of various guarding protection structures from the “EXFLU1” R&D batch by FBK, tested under different operating conditions (i.e. temperature and fluence), were accurately reproduced through simulations [5]. Utilising a

validated framework based on the “Perugia Modified Doping” TCAD model [3], a new series of simulations was produced on GR design strategies optimised for 55 μm -thick high-resistivity n-type substrates. The results of these simulations have supported the ongoing production of a new sensor batch, referred to as the “NLGAD” R&D batch, at FBK in the framework of the “eXFlu-innova” project.

In general, GR structures without any floating GRs (GR0) exhibited a breakdown voltage comparable to GR1 and GR3 design options, both before and after irradiation. Therefore, GR0 structures represent a viable design option for both p- and n-type substrates. Specifically, for p-type substrates, an improvement in the breakdown voltage of GR0 structures was achieved by increasing the overhang size of the metal contact over the bias ring. Additionally, for almost all n-in-p GR structures, popcorn noise was observed near the sensor breakdown under external bias and beyond the SEB limit [8], both before and after irradiation. Meanwhile for n-type substrates, simulations indicated that reducing the distance between the floating GR and the bias ring can lead to an improvement in the breakdown voltage of GR1 structures.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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